

LIFE, WORKS AND STORIES OF ADIL YAKUBOV.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7414557>

Odil Yaqubov (1926.20.10, present-day Karnok village, South Kazakhstan region - 2009, Tashkent) is the People's Writer of Uzbekistan (1985). Participant of World War 2. Graduated from the Faculty of Philology of Tosh State University (1956), literary consultant at the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan (1955-59), special correspondent of "Literaturnaya Gazeta" in Uzbekistan (1959-63; 1967-70), "Uzbekfilm" film studio and Uzbekistan chief editor at the state cinematography committee (1963-67), deputy editor-in-chief at Gafur Ghulam Literature and Art Publishing House (1970-82), editor-in-chief of the "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan" newspaper (1982-87), first secretary of the board of the Union of Writers of Uzbekistan (1987-91), chairman of the Terminology Committee under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (since 1991) and first vice-president of the Assembly of Cultures of the Peoples of Central Asia (since 1995) His first work - the short story "Peers" was published in 1951. "First Step" (1953), "Ikki Muhabbat" (1955), a collection of short stories, "Golden Ring" (1961) describes love as a great, sacred quality characteristic of a person. In the short story "Muqaddas" (1960), Adil Yaqubov's style and path characteristic of a true writer were revealed. In this work, the issue of returning to the right path of a young man who started to go down the path of selfishness is written. The novel "If the work falls on the head..." (1966) is about the life behind the front during the Second World War, the heroism of labor, the patriotism and bravery of our people. "Bir feleton kissasi" (1961), "Kanot juft boladi", "Matluba" (1970) and many other stories describe the heroic struggle of young people against the conflicts in marriage, and love. The novel "Treasure of Ulugbek" (1973) is a work about social relations during the time of scientist and ruler Ulugbek, the struggle between light and darkness in our distant past. The novel has many sad destinies and tragedies, but there is an optimistic spirit - faith in human thinking and the celebration of goodness. destiny is sealed. The novels "Diyonat" (1977), "White Birds, White Birds" (1988), "Adolat Manzili" (1998) truthfully describe the scenes of the life and struggle of the Uzbek people in the 60s and 70s of the 20th century. Although the main characters of these works are representatives of different fields, their characters are different, but they are similar to each other in their

destinies, goals and aspirations. They are strong-willed, brave and noble people who lived in a ignoble system and experienced many injustices and tragedies, but worked tirelessly and fought, built the foundation of national independence. With these novels, Odil Yaqubov significantly strengthened the social spirit, sharp conflict, characters, psychology in Uzbek prose, enriched it with new characters and new artistic conclusions. , plays such as "Yurak yonmoggi kerak" (1958), "Olma Gulaganda" (1961), "Muzaffar Temur" (1996), "Bir Koshona Sirlari" (2000), screenplays of "Dilbarim", "Spring Rains" (1971) author. Odil Yakubov is a skilled translator, critic, publicist. He has literary portraits and articles devoted to the works of Abdulla Qadiri, Gafur Ghulam, Oybek, Abdulla Qahhor, Hamid Olimjon, Abdulla Oripov and others. His works have been translated into foreign languages, as well as the languages of the brotherly Turkic peoples. Literary scholars Matyakub Koshjanov, Ozod Sharafiddinov, Leonid Terakoyan, Umarali Normatov, Norboy Khudoyberganov, Botir Norboyev and others have done scientific research on the work of Odil Yakubov. Laureate of the State Prize of Uzbekistan named after Hamza (1977), "Dostlik" (1994), was awarded the Order of "Respect of the Country" (1998). O. Yakubov. Election (3 toms). Tashkent. G. Ghulam Literature and Art Publishing House, 1985-1987.O. Yakubov. Religion. Tashkent. G. Ghulam Literature and Art Publishing House, 1978. His first work - the short story "Peers" was published in 1951. "The First Step" (1953), "Two Loves" (1955), a collection of short stories, "The Golden Ring" (1961) describes love as a great, sacred human emotion.In the story "Holy" (1960). The writer's style and path, characteristic of a true writer, were revealed. In this work, the question of the return of a young man, who started to go down the path of selfishness, to the right path is written. The novel "If the work falls on the head..." (1966) is about the life behind the front during the Second World War, the heroism of labor, the patriotism and courage of our people. In the short stories "Bir felyeton kissasi" (1961), "Kanot juft boladi", "Matluba" (1970) and many other stories, the brave struggle of young people against conflicts in marriage, love is described. The novel "Treasure of Ulugbek" (1973) is a work about social relations during the time of scientist and ruler Ulugbek, the struggle between light and darkness in our distant past. The novel has many sad destinies and tragedies, but there is an optimistic spirit - human thinking and faith in the celebration of goodness. In the novel "Old World" (1982), the tragic fate of the scientists Ibn Sina and Beruni, who lived in the Middle Ages and made a great contribution to the development of world science, was written. The novels "Diyanat" (1977), "White Birds, White Birds" (1988), "The Address of Justice" (1998) truthfully describe

the life and struggles of the Uzbek people in the 60s and 70s of the 20th century. Although the main characters of these works are representatives of different fields and have different characters, they are similar to each other in terms of fate, goals and aspirations. They are strong-willed, brave and noble people who lived in a ignoble system and experienced many injustices and tragedies, but worked tirelessly and fought, built the foundation of national independence. With these novels, Yakubov significantly strengthened the social spirit, sharp conflict, characters, and psychologism in Uzbek prose, enriched it with new characters and new artistic conclusions.

Yaqubov "True Love" (1955), "I Tell My Tongue, If I Don't Tell My Tongue Burns", "The Heart Needs a Burn" (1958), "When the Apple Blossoms" (1961), "Muzaffar Temur" (1996), "Bir Koshona Sirlari" (2000), the author of such plays as "Dilbarim", "Baqor Yomgirlari" (1971). O. Yakubov's first short story entitled "Peers" was published in 1951. Later, the writer published short stories such as "Muqaddas", "Tilla Uzuk", "Bir feleton kissasi", "Larza", "Kanot juft bolad", "Matluba", "Izlayman", "Billur Kandillar". Yaqubov's works "Er birshigi tush", "Treasure of Ulugbek", "Religion", "Old world", "White birds, white birds", "The destination of justice" became the basis for the appearance of psychological novels in Uzbek literature. O. Yaqubov's dramas such as "True Love", "When the Apple Blossoms", "The Heart Needs a Burn", "I Tell You, My Tongue Burns, I Don't Tell You", "Fatihi Muzaffar Yahud bir Parivash Asiri", "Bir Koshona Secrets" are important in the history of Uzbek theater. becomes important. He has literary portraits and articles devoted to the works of Abdulla Qadiri, Gafur Ghulam, Oybek, Abdulla Qahhor, Hamid Olimjon, Abdulla Oripov and others. His works have been translated into foreign languages, as well as the languages of the brotherly Turkic peoples. Odil Yaqubov also gained fame as a skilled translator, critic, and publicist. Literary experts Matyakub Koshjanov, Ozod Sharafiddinov, Leonid Terakoyan, Umarali Normashov, Norboy Khudoyberganov, Botir Norboyev and others have done research on Yakubov's work. He was awarded the State Prize of Uzbekistan named after Hamza (1977), "Friendship" (1994), "Respect of the Country" (1998) orders.

References:

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